

FORMATION OF SKILLS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING FOR FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS TO WORK IN THE CONDITIONS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Safarova Z. G.

Independent researcher

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

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Abstract. *Children with special educational needs are justified by the fact that they do not have the skills to work with children, they do not have enough knowledge about special technologies and methods of teaching such children, there is excitement, fear and distrust. Many teachers claim that children with special educational needs are an additional burden and responsibility in the classroom. Most of the answers indicate that they are not ready to work with students with special needs, training and retraining of personnel is necessary.*

In the psychological dictionary, the concept of "professional training" is defined as "the subjective state of a person who considers himself capable and ready to carry out a certain professional activity and strives to carry it out."

Keywords: *modern, innovative, startup, gaming, educational, education*

Scientific and practical foundations of the formation of skills for work in the context of inclusive education in future English teachers in the process of professional training.

The development of Science in our republic is important in instilling our national values in the minds of the younger generation in a period when the third Renaissance was laying the foundations, including the development of speech by students with disabilities. In accordance with the professional standard, teachers should use special approaches and use inclusive technologies in order to involve children with special educational needs in the educational process with students. Studies have shown that in terms of inclusive education, teachers know in a general sense and realize its importance, but are not yet ready to take classes in an inclusive class. Teachers justify this view by the fact that children with special educational needs do not have the skills to work with children, do not have sufficient knowledge of special technologies and methods of teaching such children, and there is excitement, fear and insecurity. Many teachers argue that children with a special educational need are an additional burden and responsibility in the child's classroom. Most of the answers indicate the unwillingness to work with students in particular need, the need for training and retraining personnel.

In the psychological dictionary, the concept of "professional training" is defined as "the subjective state of a person who considers himself capable and willing to carry out a certain professional activity and seeks to perform it." [28]

In the pedagogy of our country, preparation for professional activities is studied from different points of view.

Personal approach to preparation for professional activities (B.G.Ananov, A.N.Leontev et al.) considers as a sum of the qualities and characteristics of an individual. The specialist is classified by the stable nature of the individual and his professional awareness of his identity.

Preparation for work is formed from the very beginning; the manifestation of personality abilities is based on an understanding of the essence of the future profession.

Proponents of the task approach (Ye.P.Ilin, A.B. Leonov et al.) who have identified readiness for professional activities aimed at the performance of professional tasks by summing up opportunities as a temporary state of the individual. Some researchers (Ye.S.Slyusareva, K.M. Duray-Novakova) harmonize personal and functional approaches and interpret preparation as a set of qualities manifested on the basis of the specifics of the profession and as a state of mind that generates activity.

In the personal activity approach (M.I.Dyachenko, L.A. Kandibovich et al.), the preparation for professional activity is seen as the conscious and predictable activity that an individual undergoes at the stage of professional preparation. The dynamic structure of the preparation has the following appearance:

- 1) analysis of their own needs and needs of society;
- 2) determination of the purpose of activity;
- 3) development of a plan of further action;
- 4) applying the result of preparation in a particular situation [9].

According to the authors, readiness included the following components:

- 1) motivational-interest in the profession;
- 2) orientation-knowledge of occupational characteristics;
- 3) knowledge - awareness of obligations, tasks, methods of assessment and its significance, knowledge of working methods;
- 4) affective-volitional-the ability to control one's own feelings, responsibilities and manners;
- 5) Assessment – self-esteem ability [7].

The readiness of teachers for professional activities is also studied in terms of the validity approach (V.N.Vvedensky, A.K.Markova et al.). The formation of training in accordance with this approach consists in the ability to carry out activities based on acquired knowledge and skills. Professional awareness is considered as “the sum of knowledge and skills that determine the effectiveness of professional labor”; the volume of skills that the subject can adequately perform the tasks related to the topic; the harmony of personal qualities and characteristics; the sum of professional knowledge and personal qualities of professional importance; the combination of theoretical and practical preparation for the implementation of activities" [3]. We agree with the point of view of supporters of this approach and put forward the idea that in the process of professional training the individual is formed on the basis of the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications. In the work of many researchers, the problem of the readiness of teachers to work in inclusive education has become a frequently studied topic.

Yu.V.Shumilovskaya describes the readiness of the teacher to work with children with special educational needs as “the sum of knowledge and ideas about the characteristics of children with special educational needs, knowledge of ways and methods of working with these students in inclusive education, as well as the formation of certain personality-specific qualities that can provide this activity with stable motivation.” [7].

Inclusive readiness tarkibi includes the following components:

- 1) the sum of the reasons for working with the motivational – inclusive class;

2) cognitive-children with special educational needs knowledge of the physical and mental characteristics of individuals;

3) creative activity of the creative teacher and the desire of children with special educational needs to develop the creative potential of individuals;

4) children with a special educational need for activities to have ways and methods of implementing professional knowledge in the process of working with students.

V.V.Khitryuk interprets inclusive training as “a complex integral subjective quality that allows the successful implementation of competencies of a professional and scientific-pedagogical individual and relies on appropriate training” [54]. The author notes that psychological and pedagogical structures fall into the mystery of the inclusive readiness of the teacher. The psychological structure reflects the attitude of the individual to inclusion and is based on the properties of his nature. This motivational structural structure consists of (interest in activity), cognitive (awareness of the functions and tasks of the profession, knowledge of the means of achieving the goal), emotional (self-control, responsiveness, politeness), voluntary (attitude and self-confidence in the student) components.

The pedagogical structural structure combines the quality and skills of the individual, guaranteeing his successful activities in the conditions of inclusive education. The structural structure under study consists of constructive (planning the educational process), organizational (incorporating students into activities of different manifestations), communicative (establishing relationships with students) and reflexive (analysis of personal activities) components.

S.V.Alexina has repeatedly mentioned in her articles about the problem of children's unpreparedness to work with children (professional, psychological, methodological) with a special educational need of pedagogical personnel [5]. It consists of the content of inclusive readiness psychological (to the foundations of psychology, children with a special educational need to have knowledge about the developmental aspects of children, etc.k.) and professional (children with a special educational need to have psychological methods and methods in working with students, to be able to objectively assess students) allocate training.

S.A.Zaligaeva considers the preparation of the teacher to work in order to effectively carry out activities in the conditions of inclusive education as a result of the assimilation, knowledge formation, development of the necessary skills of the system of professional knowledge about children with special educational needs [2].

As we can see, many researchers see skills as one of the practical components of pedagogical training. Together with skills, knowledge, skills and personal qualities, they form a specialist who is ready for professional activities.

In explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language, the following descriptions are given to the concept of " skill:

1) ” skills developed through exercises and habits ” [4].

2) an action produced by repetition classified with a high degree of appropriation, lack of control, and partial conscious Regulation” [8].

3) ” a component of practical activity that manifests itself in the automatic execution of improved important actions by repeating them several times ” [4].

E.V.Catherine noted that the practical training of an inclusive class teacher consists of the following skills:

1) organizational-attracting students to various events, developing their interests and passion for studying in them, using methods of stimulating students;

2) easy explanation of information and learning material, its adaptation to the tasks of the educational process, the acquisition of skills for working with printed and electronic resources [7].

Ye. Ye. Burenina also puts forward a similar point of view in her article. He writes that the practical training of an educator for work in the conditions of inclusive education is determined by a number of factors. First of all, the teacher should be distinguished by the presence of organizational skills in himself. This implies the need for him to be able to form a children's community, to engage students in solving issues in their studies. The information criterion of practical readiness assumes the ability to work with various resources, acquire information and process it. The author introduces into the order of methodological skills the nature and laws of teaching educational subjects, the ability to apply various pedagogical technologies, ways, methods and methods of Education.

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